

Datasets for robotic monitoring of EU habitats

Simone Tolomei^{1,2}, Franco Angelini^{1,2}, Federica Bonini³, Anna Grassi³, Daniela Gigante³,
Barbara Valle^{4,5,6}, Marina Serena Borgatti⁴, Marco Caccianiga⁴, Leopoldo de Simone⁵,
Emanuele Fanfarillo^{5,6}, Tiberio Fiaschi⁵, Simona Maccherini^{5,6}, Claudia Angiolini^{5,6},
Giovanni Riviaccio⁷, Maria Carmela Caria^{6,7}, Agnese Denaro⁷, Simonetta Bagella^{6,7},
Manolo Garabini^{1,2}, Paolo Salaris^{1,2}

Abstract—To preserve biodiversity, the EU requires extensive habitat monitoring, as mandated by the EU Habitats Directive. Traditional methods rely on manual field surveys, which are labour-intensive and costly. The European Union NI project explores using robotics to assist this process, using quadrupedal robots and machine learning techniques that require large datasets. This paper presents four publicly available datasets collected by the quadrupedal robot ANYmal-C across four EU Natura 2000 habitats. These datasets include photos, videos of plant species, 3D point clouds, and robot locomotion data, offering valuable resources for research in species detection, habitat assessment, and robotics benchmarking.

Index Terms—datasets, robotic monitoring, quadrupedal robots

I. INTRODUCTION

Preserving biodiversity is quickly becoming a crucial goal to fight the effects of climate change. The European Union requires, with the Directive 92/43/EEC of the European Council (Habitats Directive 1), regular assessment of habitat health through extensive monitoring, which is labour-intensive and costly. This is traditionally done by field missions in which expert personnel measure and acquire habitat-specific indicators [1], such as total vegetation cover, number and diameter of trees, biomass volume, presence of typical species and early warning species. As the demand for extensive monitoring increases, the economic and human resource costs associated with it increase as well. The European Union project Natural

This research has received funding partially from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101016970 (Natural Intelligence), and in part by Ministry of University and Research (MUR) as part of the PON 2014-2021 "Research and Innovation" resources – Green/Innovation Action - DM MUR 1062/2021, in part by the European Union by the Next Generation EU project ECS00000017 'Ecosistema dell'Innovazione' Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE, PNRR, Spoke 9: Robotics and Automation for Health), and in part by the Italian Ministry of Education and Research in the framework of the "FoReLab" (Future-oriented Research Lab) Project (Departments of Excellence). S. Tolomei is within the Italian Doctorate in Robotics and Intelligent Machines

¹Centro di Ricerca "Enrico Piaggio", Università di Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56126 Pisa, Italy.

²Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell'Informazione, Università di Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56126 Pisa, Italy.

³Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Perugia, Italy

⁴Università degli Studi di Milano, Department of Biosciences, Via Celoria 26, 20133, Milano, Italy

⁵Department of Life Sciences, Università degli Studi di Siena, Via A. Moro 2, 53100, Siena, Italy

⁶NBFC, National Biodiversity Future Center, Palermo, Italy.

⁷University of Sassari, Department of Chemical, Physical, Mathematical and Natural Sciences, Via Vienna 2, I-07100, Sassari, Italy.

Fig. 1. Quadrupedal robot ANYmal-C collecting environmental data in alpine screes habitat. The robot is equipped with LiDAR and RGB-D cameras for capturing images, videos, and 3D point clouds to assist in automated biodiversity monitoring and habitat assessment.

Intelligence (NI) [2] aims to address these challenges through robotic-assisted monitoring. This possibility, already studied in marine [3] and airborne monitoring [4], is becoming accessible due to both the growing presence of machine learning and data-driven techniques, that can help process large amounts of unstructured data [5], and the reliability of locomotion systems in natural environments [6]. While the techniques are evolving and the reliability of the results is increasing, the applicability to habitat monitoring is hindered by the necessity for large amount of data.

In this work, we present four datasets for robotic monitoring acquired in four habitats of the Natura 2000 network: dunes [7], grasslands [8], forests [9] and screes [10]. The data are acquired during field missions using a quadrupedal robot ANYmal-C [11]. The datasets comprehend photos of typical species and early warning species, video recordings, 3D point clouds and recorded robot states. The latter includes locomotion-related parameters, such as joint efforts, battery consumption and temperatures. The datasets are freely available on Zenodo¹ and can be useful to the research community

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8314728>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7385369>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10013693>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8123333>

in a variety of fields. Robotic engineers, for example, can use 3D point clouds and robot status data to benchmark the robot’s performance or validate their algorithm. Moreover, botanists and computer scientists aiming to test machine learning algorithms for the detection and classification of species can analyze the plant videos and images captured by the robot to evaluate the data quality and the condition of the habitat. To this end, we created a *community* on Zenodo² to favour interdisciplinary collaborations.

II. DATA COLLECTION AND METHODOLOGY

The dataset collection was conducted by a team of robotic and botanists researchers. Data acquisition was carried out using the robot ANYmal-C, made by ANYbotics. Tab. I reports the location and habitats of the fieldwork. Every field mission was carried out during the blooming season of the species of interest, to maximize collectible data.

TABLE I
LOCATIONS OF FIELD WORK

Habitat	Location
Screes Habitat (8110 & 8120)	Stelvio National Park
Forests Habitat (9210*)	La Verna, Monte Penna
Grasslands Habitat (6210*)	Monte Maggio & Valsorda
Dunes Habitat (2110 & 2120)	La Maddalena Archipelago & Platamona Beach

Environmental data are gathered using the robot’s sensors, which comprehends a LiDAR sensor and four RGB-D cameras. Specifically, the four Intel RealSense D435 cameras capture full HD RGB images and/or 30 fps videos, while the LiDAR Velodyne VLP-16 puck lite creates a 3D map of the surroundings.

The data gathered by the robot was also collected by following a procedure as similar as possible to standard botanists’ procedure [1]. For grasslands, screes and forests, the standard procedure is to survey the area of interest by following a grid of equally spaced points (often 1m) and collecting data at each point. In dunes, the area of interest is a transect that starts from the seaside and climbs to the top of the dune.

The robot’s state was recorded using the freely available Rosbag framework, and is composed of base position and orientation, joint position, velocity, acceleration, torque, detected contact, and estimated contact forces and wrenches. Together with the data, we made available MATLAB scripts³ to extract the data and plot the values of interest. The 3D point clouds are computed by the robot’s own SLAM algorithm and are saved in XYZ Point Cloud .ply file.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The datasets provide a rich, multidisciplinary resource, containing 360 photos and 39 videos of early warning species, 1331 photos and 154 videos of typical species, as well as robot state recordings and 3D point clouds. These data, gathered across four distinct Natura 2000 habitats, allow for the development and testing of plant identification algorithms, habitat

TABLE II
DATASET COMPOSITION

Robot’s state recordings	16
Acquired 3D Point Cloud	17
Early Warning Species	360 photos 39 videos
Photos of Typical Species	1331 photos 154 videos

assessment techniques, and robotic performance metrics. The inclusion of locomotion data, such as joint forces and contact measurements, enables in-depth analysis of robot behavior in varied environments. MATLAB scripts are also provided for easy extraction and analysis of this data.

The datasets and the community built around them encourages interdisciplinary collaboration, offering a shared platform for improving robotic monitoring techniques and advancing automated habitat conservation efforts.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Gigante, F. Attorre, R. Venanzoni, A. Acosta, E. Agrillo, M. Aleffi, N. Alessi, M. Allegranza, P. Angelini, C. Angiolini *et al.*, “A methodological protocol for annex i habitats monitoring: the contribution of vegetation science,” *Plant Sociology*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 77–87, 2016.
- [2] F. Angelini, P. Angelini, C. Angiolini, S. Bagella, F. Bonomo, M. Caccianiga, C. D. Santina, D. Gigante, M. Hutter, T. Nanayakkara, P. Remagnino, D. Torricelli, and M. Garabini, “Robotic Monitoring of Habitats: The Natural Intelligence Approach,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 72 575–72 591, 2023.
- [3] M. Dunbabin and L. Marques, “Robots for environmental monitoring: Significant advancements and applications,” *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 24–39, 2012.
- [4] S. Strumia, M. Buonanno, G. Aronne, A. Santo, and A. Santangelo, “Monitoring of plant species and communities on coastal cliffs: Is the use of unmanned aerial vehicles suitable?” *Diversity*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 149, 2020.
- [5] M. Besson, Marc Besson, J. Alison, Jamie Alison, K. Bjerger, Kim Bjerger, T. E. Gorochoowski, Thomas E. Gorochoowski, T. T. Høye, Toke T. Høye, T. Jucker, Tommaso Jucker, H. M. R. Mann, Hjalte M. R. Mann, C. F. Clements, and Christopher F. Clements, “Towards the fully automated monitoring of ecological communities,” *Ecology Letters*, vol. 25, no. 12, pp. 2753–2775, Oct. 2022.
- [6] L. F. Oliveira, A. P. Moreira, and M. F. Silva, “Advances in forest robotics: A state-of-the-art survey,” *Robotics*, vol. 10, no. 2, p. 53, 2021.
- [7] F. Angelini, M. J. Pollayil, G. Rivieccio, M. C. Caria, S. Bagella, and M. Garabini, “Robotic monitoring of dunes: A dataset from the EU habitats 2110 and 2120 in Sardinia (Italy),” *Scientific Data*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 238, Feb. 2024.
- [8] F. Angelini, M. J. Pollayil, F. Bonini, D. Gigante, and M. Garabini, “Robotic monitoring of grasslands: A dataset from the EU Natura2000 habitat 6210* in the central Apennines (Italy),” *Scientific Data*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 418, Jun. 2023.
- [9] M. J. Pollayil, F. Angelini, L. de Simone, E. Fanfarillo, T. Fiaschi, S. Maccherini, C. Angiolini, and M. Garabini, “Robotic monitoring of forests: A dataset from the EU habitat 9210* in the Tuscan Apennines (central Italy),” *Scientific Data*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 845, Dec. 2023.
- [10] F. Angelini, M. J. Pollayil, B. Valle, M. S. Borgatti, M. Caccianiga, and M. Garabini, “Robotic monitoring of Alpine screes: A dataset from the EU Natura2000 habitat 8110 in the Italian Alps,” *Scientific Data*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 855, Dec. 2023.
- [11] M. Hutter, C. Gehring, A. Lauber, F. Gunther, C. D. Bellicoso, V. Tsounis, P. Fankhauser, R. Diethelm, S. Bachmann, M. Bloesch, H. Kolvenbach, M. Bjelonic, L. Isler, and K. Meyer, “ANYmal - toward legged robots for harsh environments,” *Advanced Robotics*, vol. 31, no. 17, pp. 918–931, Sep. 2017.

²<https://zenodo.org/communities/rem2022/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

³<https://github.com/CentroEPIaggio/Code-for-Habitat-Data-Analysis>